
The Evolving Value of the MBA: External Factors and Career Impact

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Abstract:

Purpose: This paper explores the perceived value of MBA programs from an international perspective, based on empirical data collected in Poland. It aims to understand how professionals assess the impact of MBA studies on career advancement, skill development, and especially professional networking, within a broader global debate on the role and relevance of management education.

Design/Methodology/Approach: A quantitative survey was conducted among 132 MBA graduates in Poland across multiple industries. The analysis focused on motivations, networking effectiveness, and perceived outcomes, using statistical methods such as correlation and variance analysis. The study draws on international literature on MBA programs and professional development.

Findings: Networking and personal growth were identified as the most valuable outcomes, surpassing traditional indicators like promotion or academic knowledge. A moderate positive correlation was found between effective networking during studies and the expansion of professional contacts. Despite recent public scandals affecting local institutions, most graduates retained a positive view of their MBA experience.

Practical recommendations: Business schools should enhance structured, internationalized networking opportunities, strengthen program credibility, and tailor content to experienced professionals in diverse global markets.

Originality value: This is one of the few empirical studies analyzing MBA program outcomes in Central and Eastern Europe. It contributes internationally relevant insights into how MBA programs function across different cultural and institutional environments.

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1. Introduction

Master of Business Administration (MBA) programs have long been recognized as pivotal in shaping leadership, strategic thinking, and professional mobility across global business landscapes. Since their inception in the early 20th century, MBAs have evolved from rigid, technocratic curricula into dynamic, interdisciplinary platforms that integrate sustainability, innovation, and digital transformation (Khurana, 2007; Bridgman, Cummings, and McLaughlin, 2018).

Their popularity remains strong among mid-career professionals worldwide, driven by the promise of accelerated career progression, expanded networks, and enhanced managerial competence (Graduate Management Admission Council, 2023).

Despite the global reach and theoretical endorsement of MBA programs, their practical value varies across regions and institutional contexts. In Anglo-American environments, an MBA often serves as an informal prerequisite for executive roles.

However, in other parts of the world, such as Central and Eastern Europe, including Poland, the MBA remains an optional – and sometimes contested – credential. In recent years, the Polish media has raised concerns about the integrity and quality of local MBA offerings, particularly those provided by private or unaccredited institutions. Reports of diploma mills and the issuance of degrees with minimal academic requirements have damaged public trust and sparked debates on the commodification of business education (Iwaniuk, 2024; Gryn, 2025).

Notwithstanding these challenges, interest in MBA education continues to grow among Polish professionals. This is largely attributed to the perceived value of personal development, managerial upskilling, and – perhaps most notably – professional networking.

Networking is widely acknowledged in international literature as a central pillar of the MBA experience, providing access to informal knowledge exchange, career opportunities, and social capital (Wieser, 2016; Awaysheh and Bonfiglio, 2017). Yet, while the structural and cultural role of MBA programs in Western contexts has

been extensively researched (McDonald, 2017; Saïd and Alsultanny, 2019), empirical data concerning the Polish experience remains scarce.

This study aims to address this gap by offering an evidence-based analysis of the motivations, outcomes, and perceived value of MBA programs among Polish graduates. It situates the findings within the broader international discourse on management education, arguing that while global best practices shape program content and delivery, local socio-economic and institutional conditions significantly mediate their perceived effectiveness.

The originality of this research lies in its empirical focus on the lived experiences of MBA graduates in Poland – a country where, unlike in the U.S. or U.K., formal credentials do not necessarily translate into executive roles. The study draws on quantitative data collected via an online survey administered to 132 Polish MBA graduates, most of whom completed part-time or executive programs while working full-time in sectors such as finance, consulting, IT, and healthcare.

By examining how these individuals assess the impact of their MBA education – particularly in terms of networking, career advancement, and skill development – the study contributes localized insights to a global conversation.

This research also engages with the changing expectations of MBA participants, particularly younger professionals from Generation Y and Z who emphasize flexibility, purpose-driven leadership, and sustainability (Graduate Management Admission Council, 2023).

It considers how institutional support for networking activities, access to alumni communities, and use of digital tools like LinkedIn influence the long-term value of MBA education. Additionally, it explores the implications of public scandals involving degree inflation for the credibility of these programs, without assuming that all MBA degrees are equally affected.

In light of these dynamics, the study is guided by the following research questions:

- *What motivates Polish professionals to pursue MBA programs in an increasingly skeptical environment?*
- *To what extent does networking during MBA studies translate into perceived career benefits?*
- *How do graduates assess the institutional support they received for building professional relationships?*
- *Are there notable gender, industry, or age-related differences in how MBA value is perceived?*
- *How do recent controversies surrounding MBA programs influence graduates' perceptions of their degrees?*

To address these questions, the article is structured as follows. The next section presents a comprehensive review of the international literature on MBA education, highlighting trends, criticisms, and contextual differences. This is followed by a description of the research methodology, including sampling, survey design, and statistical analysis techniques.

The fourth section presents the empirical findings, with a focus on demographic profiles, networking outcomes, skill development, and the perceived impact of recent controversies. The article concludes by discussing the implications of the findings for business schools, MBA applicants, and policy-makers, and proposes directions for future research in both local and cross-national contexts.

By focusing on the under-explored Polish perspective, this study contributes to a more nuanced, internationally relevant understanding of how MBA programs function as tools for professional development – and how their value is negotiated within specific socio-institutional settings.

2. Literature Review

Master Since their establishment in the early 20th century, Master of Business Administration (MBA) programs have evolved in tandem with global economic developments and shifting paradigms in managerial education. Initially designed to deliver a structured and scientific approach to business management, these programs have progressively broadened their scope to include emerging domains such as digital transformation, intercultural competence, and sustainable leadership (Khurana, 2007; McDonald, 2017).

Historically, the genesis of the MBA is closely tied to the professionalization of management, marked by the founding of Harvard Business School in 1908. The post-World War II era intensified the globalization of business, prompting institutions to diversify curricula through specializations like marketing, international business, and human resource management, thereby aligning education with practical demands of multinational enterprises (Alghaithi and Sartawi, 2020).

The 1970s and 1980s witnessed a significant international expansion of the MBA model. Institutions such as INSEAD and the London Business School played a pivotal role in adapting the American model to European and Asian markets, placing a greater emphasis on cross-cultural competence and strategic leadership. Concurrently, the development of Executive MBA (EMBA) programs responded to the growing need for flexible educational formats tailored to experienced professionals (McDonald, 2017).

The advent of the digital economy in the 21st century significantly influenced MBA structures, both in content and in delivery modes. Curricula were enriched with modules in IT management, e-commerce, project management, and digital

marketing (Bridgman, Cummings, and McLaughlin, 2018). Moreover, the rise of online MBA programs democratized access to business education, enabling broader participation from geographically dispersed professionals (Graduate Management Admission Council, 2023).

Contemporary MBA programs are increasingly shaped by normative pressures toward ethical leadership, social responsibility, and sustainability. These are no longer peripheral topics but central themes integrated through experiential learning, coaching, and partnerships with corporations and NGOs (Awaysheh and Bonfiglio, 2017).

Nevertheless, MBA programs have been subject to criticism. Scholars and practitioners point to a gap between academic theory and business practice, questioning whether traditional curricula adequately prepare students for volatile, uncertain, complex, and ambiguous (VUCA) environments. In response, some institutions have introduced interdisciplinary modules focusing on soft skills, innovation, and stakeholder engagement (Bridgman *et al.*, 2018).

The issue of return on investment (ROI) has become particularly salient. Empirical studies confirm that MBA graduates often experience salary growth and upward career mobility, yet concerns persist about tuition fees, opportunity costs, and disparities in program quality. Moreover, intangible benefits such as professional networks, strategic thinking capabilities, and personal development are increasingly emphasized in the value proposition of MBA programs (Graduate Management Admission Council, 2023).

Generational dynamics also play a significant role. Millennials and Generation Z demonstrate distinct expectations, often prioritizing work-life balance, sustainability, and purpose-driven careers over hierarchical advancement. As a result, MBA programs have incorporated themes such as stakeholder capitalism, climate risk, and innovation for sustainability (Awaysheh and Bonfiglio, 2017).

The proliferation of alternative executive education paths - such as microcredentials, online certificates, and domain-specific master's degrees - has intensified competition. These options, often characterized by shorter duration and lower cost, compel traditional business schools to emphasize international accreditation, alumni engagement, and personalized career services as differentiators (Alghaithi and Sartawi, 2020).

In an influential empirical study, Wieser (2016) applied the Inputs–Environment–Outcomes (I-E-O) model to examine gender-based differentials in the MBA experience. Using data from 787 alumni across 41 programs in Europe and the United States, the study revealed structural inequalities, particularly in leadership confidence and access to informal networks, underscoring the need for curricular reform to address both technical skills and equity concerns.

A comparative analysis by Saïd and Alsultanny (2019) focused on MBA students in France and the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) region. Despite cultural differences, students shared similar motivations: career advancement and leadership development. However, program preferences diverged: GCC students prioritized entrepreneurial autonomy, whereas French students valued international mobility and strategic planning competencies.

Ahmed (2025) investigated the impact of MBA programs on career trajectories among professionals with engineering or IT backgrounds. Through a mixed-methods approach, the study demonstrated that combining technical expertise with business acumen resulted in enhanced leadership potential, broader job mobility, and increased strategic insight.

While international discourse on MBA outcomes is well-documented, the Polish context remains under-researched. Domestic media outlets have expressed skepticism regarding the ROI of MBA programs, especially those offered by private institutions lacking international accreditation. Report in business press such as *Forbes Polska* have highlighted concerns related to tuition costs, admission transparency, and uneven program quality. This contributes to a perception of some MBA programs as status symbols rather than developmental tools (Gryn, 2025).

Moreover, the MBA's professional utility in Poland appears to diverge significantly from the Anglo-Saxon model. While in the United States and the United Kingdom the MBA often functions as a *de facto* requirement for executive leadership roles, in the Polish context it is frequently viewed as optional or even superfluous - particularly in sectors where professional advancement is driven by tenure, interpersonal networks, and political capital rather than formal academic credentials.

Recent controversies surrounding the mass issuance of MBA degrees by institutions such as Collegium Humanum have further eroded public trust in the academic and professional merit of such qualifications. Investigative reports revealed that MBA diplomas were granted after minimal academic effort, raising concerns about the commodification of higher education and the use of such credentials primarily as instruments for securing positions in state-owned companies (Iwaniuk, 2024)

These contextual nuances justify the need for localized, evidence-based assessment of MBA program effectiveness. The present study aims to address this research gap by empirically analyzing the motivations, outcomes, and perceived value of MBA education among Polish professionals.

3. Research Methodology and Case Description

The aim of this study was to assess how MBA programs impact the professional development of students and graduates, with particular attention to their relevance in a changing educational and business environment. A quantitative research

methodology was adopted due to its ability to identify trends, measure correlations between variables, and generalize results.

The primary research method was an online questionnaire distributed among MBA graduates via LinkedIn. Respondents were selected based on their declared completion of MBA studies. The survey included demographic questions and items addressing motivations for enrolling in MBA programs, perceived outcomes, and career development.

The final sample included 132 respondents (66% men, 34% women), mainly aged 30–45, with varied educational and professional backgrounds. The majority had at least five years of work experience prior to starting the MBA, and represented sectors such as finance, consulting, IT, healthcare, and industry.

Most participants had completed part-time or executive MBA programs, which allowed them to combine studies with professional duties. Many respondents held middle or senior management positions at the time of the survey, and a notable proportion declared intentions to pursue international careers or switch industries following the completion of their MBA.

The research covered a broad spectrum of MBA alumni from different Polish universities. The survey tool was pre-tested to ensure clarity and eliminate potential bias.

The sample size was determined to ensure statistical relevance. With a 95% confidence level and a 9% margin of error, a minimum of 118 responses was required. Advanced statistical techniques were used to analyze the data, including regression analysis, correlation testing, and variance analysis (ANOVA), which allowed the researcher to explore relationships between educational experiences and professional advancement.

Online surveys were selected for their cost-efficiency, speed, and ease of analysis. The anonymity and comfort of remote participation ensured more honest and thoughtful responses. The methodology was designed to provide a reliable picture of how MBA education is perceived and how it supports career development in the Polish context.

4. Research Results

A survey of MBA graduates was conducted between April and September 2024. A total of 132 MBA graduates participated in the survey, including 87 men (66%) and 45 women (34%), who were willing to share their experiences and opinions. Figures 1 through 13 show the results of the surveys conducted.

The demographic data collected in the survey confirms that MBAs are not aimed at the young and inexperienced. In the survey, the age of respondents ranged from 26 to 63, indicating a diverse age group of participants. The above survey suggests that diversity in terms of work experience among the surveyed MBA graduates. To account for this diversity and to discard outliers, the analysis focused on a median age of 44 years and a mean of 43.8 indicating that the majority of the program's participants are mature, established professionals.

Figure 1. Responses from MBA graduates on question about gender of the research survey.

Source: Own elaboration.

Figure 2. Responses from MBA graduates' to question about age of the research survey

Source: Own elaboration.

The median age for the two genders differs and is respectively a median of 44 and a mean of 44.4 for women, and for men the median is 43 years a mean of 43.5. Based on the research, it can be seen that women in Poland decide to pursue MBA studies a year later than men. This phenomenon can be interpreted in the context of several key social, professional and cultural factors that influence women's educational and professional decisions.

One of the most important factors delaying women's decision to pursue an MBA is the need to balance family responsibilities with professional development. Women may need more time to build confidence and belief in their own competence before deciding to pursue an MBA.

Compared to men, women are more likely to underestimate their qualifications and abilities, which delays their decision to pursue further education. This difference in self-perception may be the result of both individual experience and broader social norms. In the following analysis, it is worth looking at, factors that influence perceptions of networking and expectations of an MBA program.

Figure 3. Responses from MBA graduates' to question about whether networking is important for professional development

Source: Own elaboration.

The results of the survey, in which the vast majority of respondents (92.4%) agreed that networking is important for professional development, confirm the importance of this issue.

In the following analysis, we will discuss in detail the aspects affecting the effectiveness of networking during the study, paying particular attention to the extent to which graduates feel supported by the university and what difficulties they encounter in the networking process.

In the survey, 92.4% of MBA graduates considered networking to be important for career development. Networking is widely recognized as a key element of career development by MBA graduates. This confirms the widespread belief in the important role of building and maintaining professional relationships in achieving success.

There is no direct relationship between perceptions of networking and the impact of an MBA on advancement. While networking is important, the survey did not find that those who consider it important are more likely to perceive the impact of an MBA on their opportunities for advancement. This may suggest that the impact of an MBA on a career is more complex and depends on many factors.

Figure 4. Responses from MBA graduates' to question about evaluating the effectiveness of networking during studies

Source: Own elaboration.

The effectiveness of networking during MBA studies has a positive impact on the development of professional contacts after completing the program. Most people rate networking very high on the scale and a significant minority rate it less than 5.

Those who rate networking as more effective are more likely to see an increase in the number and quality of their contacts. The ability to effectively establish and maintain relationships while studying translates into tangible benefits in the form of an expanded network of professional contacts.

The university's support for networking activities has a positive impact on students' networking effectiveness. Correlation analysis showed a weak positive correlation

(0.255) between the university's support rating and the networking effectiveness rating.

The university's support of networking activities may have some positive impact on students' networking effectiveness, but this impact is relatively small. MBA students should also actively seek out networking opportunities outside of those organized by the university to maximize the benefits of networking.

Figure 5. Responses from MBA graduates' to question about evaluation of the university's support of networking

Source: Own elaboration.

Figure 6. Responses from MBA graduates' to question about presence of barriers

Source: Own elaboration.

Personal and psychological barriers are rare in MBA studies but that doesn't mean they don't occur. Barriers hinder effective networking during MBA studies. 81.2% of respondents said they had not encountered personal or psychological barriers to networking. 18.8% of respondents admitted that they had experienced such difficulties. Among the respondents who encountered communication barriers during their MBA studies - 7 were women, 18 were men.

The chi-square test of the relationship between gender and encountering barriers high p-value (0.7455) suggests that there is no statistically significant relationship between gender and encountering barriers to networking during MBA studies. In other words, both women and men reported barriers to a similar degree. Overall, the most common barriers were: Lack of confidence 10 people, lack of university-organized networking opportunities 8 people social anxiety and introversion and feelings of inadequacy or imposter syndrome 7 people.

Social media platforms are an effective networking tool, enabling people to establish and nurture relationships with people from different industries and locations. At the same time, this hypothesis implies the need to compare the effectiveness of virtual and traditional networking meetings. In the following section, we will take a closer look at these issues, analyzing both the potential of new technologies and the limitations they may pose in the context of networking.

Figure 7. Responses from MBA graduates' to question about how important the role of social media in networking strategies

Source: Own elaboration.

Social media, and LinkedIn in particular, play an important role in the networking strategies of MBA graduates. The survey results indicate that LinkedIn is a key tool in MBA graduates' networking strategies.

Respondents identified LinkedIn as by far the most popular networking tool, with (62%). In second place were video conferencing apps (22%). Facebook came in third place (9%).

Figure 8. Responses from MBA graduates' to question about which online tools are most effective for networking

Source: Own elaboration.

LinkedIn's integration with other tools, such as video conferencing applications, is also popular, suggesting that respondents value the combination of online relationship-building opportunities and face-to-face communication. It is worth noting that Facebook, despite its popularity, is less frequently chosen as the main tool for professional networking compared to LinkedIn.

The results of the survey in the context of the MBA scandals suggest that the scandals have not had a significant impact on how graduates assess the value of their MBA degrees. A key element of the survey was a question that directly addressed the possible change in perceptions of the value of MBA education after the publicity surrounding the scandals associated with the universities offering these programs.

Analysis of the responses reveals an interesting paradox: despite the media hype surrounding the irregularities, graduates do not seem to have lost faith in the value of the knowledge and skills they have acquired. Analysis of the responses reveals that:

29.3% of respondents admitted that their perception of the value of MBA education changed after the scandals. 70.7% of respondents said their perception had not changed. Evaluate how these changes have affected students' and alumni's preferences and decisions to choose MBA programs.

Next, we will focus on analyzing whether the competencies gained during the MBA program translate into real career benefits, such as promotion to a higher position. 39% of respondents believe that the skills acquired during the MBA program had a direct impact on their career advancement opportunities. 34% of respondents believe that the skills acquired during the MBA program did not have a direct impact on their career advancement opportunities. The remaining respondents did not answer this question or chose the option "I'm not sure" These data suggest that the impact of MBA programs on careers is more complex and ambiguous than it might seem.

Figure 9. Responses from MBA graduates' to question about whether scandals surrounding mba studies have an impact on the perception of their value

Source: Own elaboration.

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Another important aspect of the survey is to analyze the most important benefits that respondents perceive in completing an MBA program. This question allows us to

understand what specific values graduates attribute to their MBA studies and what goals they wanted to achieve by participating in the program.

Respondents identified two main benefits of completing an MBA program: Personal development, Networking and networking. Other benefits such as ‘Acquired theoretical and practical knowledge’ and ‘Opportunity for advancement at work’ were mentioned much less frequently.

Figure 10. Responses from MBA graduates' to question about whether whether the skills acquired during the MBA program had a direct impact on career advancement opportunities

Source: Own elaboration.

Figure 11. Responses from MBA graduates' to question about the benefits respondents see in completing an MBA program.

Source: Own elaboration.

These results suggest that for the majority of respondents, the key value of an MBA is not only the acquisition of specific knowledge and skills, but above all personal development and the opportunity to make valuable professional contacts. It is worth noting that respondents identified "Networking and networking" 36.1% as one of the most important benefits gained from completing an MBA program, only surpassed by 1 percentage point by the desire for personal development 37.6%.

Although "Acquired theoretical and practical knowledge" was selected by only 19.5% of respondents, it indicates that gaining management knowledge is an important factor motivating some graduates to pursue an MBA.

Let's now turn to an analysis of the management skills that respondents consider most developed during their MBA studies. This question is important because it allows us to understand what specific competencies MBA graduates developed through the program and what areas were particularly strongly emphasized during their studies.

Figure 12. Responses from MBA graduates' to question about the management skills that respondents consider most developed during their MBA studies

Source: Own elaboration.

The survey confirms that MBA programs contribute to the development of key managerial skills. Respondents indicated a variety of managerial skills they developed during their MBA studies, but a few stand out as the most frequently mentioned. Problem solving was indicated by the largest number of respondents. Critical thinking and interpersonal communication were the next most important skills.

Leadership was also mentioned by a significant number of respondents. Other skills were indicated much less frequently, suggesting that the MBA program focuses primarily on developing competencies related to analysis, communication and management.

Figure 13. Figure showing the correlation between ratings of networking effectiveness and perceived increase in the number of contacts

Source: Own elaboration.

The effectiveness of networking during MBA studies influences the perceived increase in the number and quality of professional contacts after completing the program. An examination of the impact of networking effectiveness during MBA studies on the perceived increase in the number and quality of professional contacts after program completion revealed a significant relationship.

Across the entire group of respondents, a moderately strong positive correlation was observed between ratings of networking effectiveness and perceived increase in the number of contacts. Correlation analysis for the smaller group showed a moderately strong positive correlation (0.317) between ratings of networking effectiveness and perceived increase in the number of contacts after the MBA. In addition, an analysis of variance (ANOVA) confirmed statistically significant differences between the mean ratings of networking effectiveness among the groups of respondents who answered the question about increased number of contacts differently (F- statistic: 3.524, p-value: 0.036).

5. Conclusions and Future Research Implications

The findings of this study provide a nuanced understanding of how MBA programs influence the professional development of experienced managers in the Polish

context. The results confirm that these programs primarily attract mature professionals with established career trajectories, seeking advanced managerial competencies, personal development, and expanded professional networks.

This aligns with earlier international research emphasizing the value of MBA programs for leadership development, strategic thinking, and career mobility (Ahmed, 2025; Saïd and Alsultanny, 2019). However, the Polish MBA landscape presents distinct contextual challenges, including skepticism regarding program quality and return on investment, as highlighted in prior reports (Gryn, 2025; Iwaniuk, 2024).

One of the most consistent themes across the survey was the central role of networking. Over 92% of respondents identified networking as critical to career development, echoing findings by Wieser (2016) and McDonald (2017) that professional relationship-building is a defining feature of MBA education.

The study revealed a moderate positive correlation between networking effectiveness during studies and subsequent increases in both the number and quality of professional contacts. Notably, the effectiveness of networking was influenced not only by institutional support but also by individual initiative, underscoring the importance of fostering both structured opportunities and self-directed engagement.

The research also confirms that MBA programs significantly contribute to the development of core managerial skills, with problem-solving, critical thinking, and interpersonal communication being the most frequently cited. Interestingly, gender-based differences emerged in skill perception, with female respondents more often highlighting the development of critical thinking.

This suggests that MBA programs may hold particular value for women aiming to enhance analytical and strategic capabilities, consistent with prior findings on gendered experiences in business education (Wieser, 2016).

From a practical standpoint, the following recommendations can be drawn:

- Enhance structured networking opportunities by integrating both in-person and virtual formats, including cross-cohort collaborations, alumni mentoring, and industry partner events.
- Tailor program content to experienced professionals by incorporating advanced management techniques, emerging leadership models, and digital transformation tools.
- Address gender-specific needs through inclusive pedagogical approaches and targeted leadership development modules.
- The study's limitations should be acknowledged. The sample, while diverse in professional background, was limited to graduates of Polish MBA programs and collected via self-reported survey responses. This approach

may introduce selection bias and restrict the generalizability of findings to broader or international contexts.

Additionally, the absence of longitudinal tracking prevents assessment of long-term career impacts. Future research should:

- Expand the sample to include comparative cohorts from other countries, particularly in Central and Eastern Europe, to assess regional differences.
- Investigate the relative impact of specific MBA program components on career advancement.
- Explore the role of digital networking tools and emerging technologies, such as AI-driven career services, in shaping MBA graduates' professional trajectories.

In conclusion, this study reinforces the importance of MBA programs as platforms for personal development, strategic skill acquisition, and professional networking.

At the same time, it highlights the need for Polish institutions to adapt their curricula, delivery methods, and networking frameworks to meet the evolving expectations of experienced managers in a complex and competitive business environment. Sustained relevance will require a balance between global best practices and localized innovations tailored to the specific cultural and economic context of Poland.

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